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The role of stereotactic body radiation therapy in management of patients with pancreatic cancer

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Pancreatic cancer (PC) is the eighth leading cause of cancer-related deaths worldwide. In 2020, there were 1589 new cases in Serbia and around 1500 number of deaths. The only potentially curative therapy for PC is surgery, but only 20% patients are resectable at the time of diagnosis. Despite recent advances in the management poor survival rates continue for PC patients. Neoadjuvant conventional radiotherapy (RT) with concurrent chemotherapy (CT) requires 4-6 weeks and it is associated with the large fields with limited ability to avoid surrounding normal tissues. The advantage of stereotactic body radiation therapy (SBRT) in the treatment of PC is the fact that it is completed quickly over 1–5 fractions, requires less time away from full doses of CT, and as a result of more limited target volumes it is better tolerated than conventional RT. Indication for SBRT in PC patients include locally advanced PC in neoadjuvant setting, palliation of pain, elderly patients who are not surgical candidates, local therapy in oligometastatic cases or it can be used as a salvage treatment for local failures after surgery or conventional RT. Performing SBRT with targets that may move during respiration is challenging. Respiration induced motion of target volume can be reduced by introduction of motion management strategies such as infrared markers, deep inspiration breath hold, abdominal compression, respiratory tracking and gating. New RT units allow us to deliver dose more precisely and to make dose escalation. Different regimes of fractionation are optional, from a single fraction (25 Gy in 1 fraction) to hypo-fractionation regimes (24-36 Gy in 5 fractions). Much of the data published on the use of SBRT in PC refers to delaying local progression in locally advanced cases and improving R0 resection rates and local control, also with benefit in patients' quality of life. With adequate selection of PC patients the implementation of SBRT, especially in combina-

tion with effective systematic treatment modalities, can provide better local control with extension of survival.

Keywords: *pancreatic cancer, stereotactic body radiation therapy, conventional chemoradiotherapy.*

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